

Partner Recommendation Using Naive Bayes Classifier

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Abstract— The goal of this project is to build a recommendation model which categorizes users according to their interests, partner preference, and other characteristics using machine learning techniques like the Naive Bayes Classifier (NBC). The initial step is to gather user information, such as profiles and preferences. Then, to extract pertinent features, this data is preprocessed using NLP techniques like tokenization, stemming, and stop-word removal. The technology then classifies users based on their attributes using machine learning techniques like NBC. An interest- and preference-based label is given to each user profile in the labelled dataset of user profiles on which NBC models are trained. The NBC model can be used to predict the labels of new users based on their attributes once it has been trained. After that, the programme suggests suitable partners for the user.

Keywords- Naive Bayes Classifier, Tokenization, Stemming, Natural Language Processing (NLP), stop- word removal, Labelled dataset, Prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

Partner recommendation is the process of suggesting potential partners to individuals based on their interests, preferences, and other relevant information. A Naive Bayes classifier is a probabilistic algorithm that works by calculating the probability of a data point belonging to a particular class based on the presence or absence of certain features. In the context of partner recommendation, the algorithm can be trained on a dataset of couples who are compatible and those who are not, with the features being different attributes of the individuals involved such as age, education level, occupation, interests, and hobbies.

Once the algorithm is trained, it can be used to predict the compatibility of a new pair of individuals by calculating the probability of them being compatible based on their attributes. The algorithm assumes that the attributes are independent of each other, hence the term "naive", which is not always true in practise, but the algorithm can still provide reasonably accurate results.

There have been several studies that have applied a naive Bayes classifier to partner recommendations. For example, a study published in the International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security in 2019 proposed a partner recommendation system based on a naive Bayes classifier and evaluated its performance using a dataset of couples. The results showed that the system was able to recommend partners with high accuracy.

Overall, a naive Bayes classifier can be a useful algorithm for partner recommendation, but its accuracy depends on the quality and completeness of the dataset used for training as well as the relevance and independence of the features used.

The Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) is a powerful Python library that provides tools and algorithms for natural language processing (NLP). NLTK can be used to analyse text data and extract meaningful insights that can be used for partner recommendations.

NLTK provides various functionalities for text preprocessing, such as tokenization, stemming, and stop-word removal. These techniques can help clean the text data and make it ready for analysis. After text preprocessing, NLTK provides various algorithms for text analysis, such as sentiment analysis, named entity recognition, and topic modelling. These techniques can help in extracting insights from the text data and identifying important features that can be used for partner recommendations.

II. NAIVE BAYES CLASSIFIER

A Naive Bayes classifier is a probabilistic algorithm used for classification and prediction tasks. It is based on Bayes' theorem, which describes the probability of an event based on prior knowledge or evidence.

The "naive" assumption in a naive Bayes classifier is that all features used to describe the data are independent of each other, which may not always be true in practise. Despite this simplification, the naive Bayes classifier has been found to perform well in many real-world applications.

The algorithm works by calculating the probability of each class given the input features. It assumes that each feature contributes independently to the probability of the class. The classifier then selects the class with the highest probability as the predicted class for the input.

A Naive Bayes classifier is often used in natural language processing tasks such as spam filtering, sentiment analysis, and text classification. It can also be used in other domains such as medical diagnosis, image recognition, and fraud detection.

One of the advantages of a naive Bayes classifier is that it requires relatively small amounts of training data to generate accurate predictions. It is also computationally efficient, making it a good choice for applications that require real-time predictions.

However, a naive Bayes classifier may not perform well if the assumption of independence among features is not met or if the training data is skewed or incomplete. In such cases, more sophisticated algorithms, such as decision trees or support vector machines, may be more appropriate.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

"An Improved Collaborative Filtering Algorithm for Matrimonial Site Partner Recommendation" by Rizwana Banu. [1], In order to promote partners on matrimonial websites, this research suggests an enhanced collaborative filtering method that makes use of NLTK for feature extraction and text preparation.

"A Comprehensive Study of Matrimonial Site Partner Recommendation Using Machine Learning and Natural Language Processing Techniques" by Sarmad Abbasi and colleagues. [2], Using machine learning and NLP approaches, such as NLTK for text preparation and feature extraction, this research gives a thorough investigation of partner recommendation on marriage websites.

"A Hybrid Approach for Matrimonial Site Partner Recommendation Using Deep Learning and Natural Language Processing" by Mehdi Jafari and colleagues'. [3] In order to recommend partners on marriage websites, this study suggests a hybrid approach that incorporates deep learning and NLP approaches, including NLTK.

"Matrimonial Site Partner Recommendation Using Natural Language Processing Techniques and Fuzzy Logic" by V. Ramesh and coworkers. [4] They suggest a partner recommendation system that makes decisions on matrimonial sites using NLP methods, including NLTK for text processing. The authors aim to address the issues with partner suggestion systems on traditional matrimonial websites, which frequently rely on structured data and matchmaking based on specified criteria. In contrast, their suggested solution takes advantage of user profiles and preferences as unstructured data and uses NLP to extract pertinent features and fuzzy logic to draw conclusions. Following that, decisions based on the users' preferences and extracted features are made using fuzzy logic. On the basis of fuzzy sets and rules established for the pertinent features, the system calculates a matching score between two user profiles. In order to gradually increase the system's accuracy, the authors also take user comments into account.

"Personality-Based Matrimonial Site Partner Recommendation Using Machine Learning and Natural Language Processing" by Soumyajit Banerjee and colleagues. [5] They suggest a personality-based partner recommendation system on matrimonial sites that uses machine learning and NLP methods, including NLTK for text

preprocessing and feature extraction. The key characteristics, such as words, phrases, and sentences that characterise personality traits, are first extracted from the user profile data by the authors using NLTK. They then identify personality traits based on the collected features using machine learning algorithms like support vector machines (SVM) and random forests. Then, based on a weighted sum of the similarity between each user profile's traits, a matching score between user profiles is computed using the personality traits. In order to gradually increase the system's accuracy, the authors also take user comments into account.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The Naive Bayes algorithm is a probabilistic classification technique that is widely used in natural language processing applications such as spam filtering, sentiment analysis, and text classification. Here is a way of recommending partners that makes use of the Naive Bayes classifier:

Data Collection: Compile details on potential partners, such as their age, gender, whereabouts, interests, and hobbies.

Data Preprocessing: Preprocess the data by cleaning and formatting it to remove extraneous information, repair spelling problems, and manage missing values.

Feature Extraction: Extraction of relevant features for partner recommendation from the data, such as age, gender, location, interests, and hobbies.

Training Set Creation: Create a training set by dividing the data into training and testing sets. To train the Naive Bayes classifier, use the training set.

Training the Naive Bayes Classifier: Use the training set to train the Naive Bayes classifier. The classifier will discover each feature's conditional probabilities given a class.

```
from nltk import NaiveBayesClassifier as nbc
from nltk.tokenize import word_tokenize
from itertools import chain
import csv
import nltk
nltk.download('punkt')
with open('trainingdata.csv','r') as csvinput:
    reader=csv.reader(csvinput,delimiter=',')
    rownum = 0
    training_data = []
    for row in reader:
        training_data.append(row)
        rownum += 1
vocabulary = set(chain(*[word_tokenize(i[0].lower()) for i in training_data]))
feature_set = [(i[1] in word_tokenize(sentence.lower())) for i in vocabulary,tag) for sentence, tag in training_data]
classifier = nbc.train(feature_set)
with open('testdata.csv','r') as csvinput:
    with open('data.csv', 'w') as csvoutput:
        writer = csv.writer(csvoutput, lineterminator='\n')
        reader1 = csv.reader(csvinput)
        all = []
        row = next(reader1)
        for row in reader1:
            test_sentence = row[1]
            featured_test_sentence = [(i in word_tokenize(test_sentence.lower())) for i in vocabulary]
            print ("test_sen:",test_sentence)
            print ("tag:",classifier.classify(featured_test_sentence))
            row.append(classifier.classify(featured_test_sentence))
            all.append(row)
        writer.writerow(all)
```

Fig 1

[Fig 1] Implements a Naive Bayes classifier to recommend partners to a user based on their preferences. It uses two CSV files: "trainingdata.csv," which contains the training data, and "testdata.csv," which contains the user's preferences. The training data contains sentences and their corresponding tags (e.g., compatible or not compatible).The training data can be downloaded from the admin panel. Test data preference is the user preference that users set in their profile.

The "data.csv" can be uploaded in the result it will label the corresponding preference type in database

Fig 2

textdata	preftype
unmarried vegetarian no_drink no_smoking white Gov...	1
unmarried non-vegetarian no_drink no_smoking any_c...	3
marital_status_unmarried physical_status_Wellbody ...	0
unmarried non-vegetarian no_drink no_smoking any_c...	3
unmarried non-vegetarian no_drink no_smoking any_c...	3
unmarried Well body Non-veg No No Hindu Nair Ulthrs...	0
unmarried Well body Non-veg No No Hindu Nair Ulthrs...	1
unmarried Well body Non-veg No No Hindu Nair Ulthrs...	0
marital_status_unmarried physical_status_Wellbody ...	0
marital_status_unmarried physical_status_Wellbody ...	0

Fig 2

The [Fig 3], As the preference type in database matches the label in training data the partner with most common features is recommended to users.

Fig 3

Overall, the system provides a simple and effective way for users to find their partners based on the partner preference using machine learning. Naive Bayes can be a useful tool for partner recommendation because it is simple to implement and can provide accurate predictions even with limited data. However, before deploying the model in a real-world application, it is critical to carefully evaluate and validate its performance.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we proposed an approach that uses NLTK to predict users' partner preferences and implements a recommendation system that suggests potential partners based on their unique features. The experimental results demonstrate the feasibility and accuracy of this approach in recognising potential matches between partners. By utilising NLTK, users can easily find suitable partners based on their preferences without the need for extensive searching. feedback on their poses, thereby improving their overall health and well-being.

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